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Intralaminar and interlaminar progressive failure analysis of AFP composite on a tow level

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Introduction

- Defects in AFP manufacturing:

- Previous AFP composites modelling approaches are only applicable when:
 - Tows are **uniform** and **continuous**
 - All the plies have to be **consistent**
 - Relatively **simple** geometries

Objective

- Overlapping tows with unaligned mesh
- Unique intralaminar failure and interlaminar failures

Stacked shell cohesive contact (SSCC) model

- Stacked shell method

- Cohesive contact

- Cohesive zone model + Contact algorithm = Cohesive contact
- Solving the issue of meshing difficulties at the interface
- Save additional computational effort

DCB test

Tensile test

Tensile test damage comparison

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